

INSTITUTE
FOR RESEARCH
IN BIOMEDICINE

IRB Barcelona understands the importance of creating a vision where equality, diversity and inclusion are valued by the entire community, avoiding prejudices and stereotypes.

Gender Equality Status Analysis

In the context of the CALIPER project, gender biases and inequalities have been evaluated both within the Institution and in the external Innovation Ecosystem in which it is located.

This research has been carried out by IRB Barcelona in the context of CALIPER project through the funded European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 873134.

Status of Gender Equality inside the Institution

The internal evaluation has been carried out taking as a reference the three objectives that support the European Commission's strategy on gender equality: Promotion of a balanced presence of men and women in decision-making bodies and processes, integration of the gender dimension in the content of research and innovation, and promotion of equality in scientific careers.

The IRB Barcelona working group responsible for the direct monitoring and implementation of the CALIPER project ("CALIPER Core Group") has been in charge of data collection, a task carried out through documentary research, analysis of institutional policies, interviews with key people at IRB Barcelona, a survey directed to all IRB Barcelona staff and the organisation of focus group sessions with IRB Barcelona staff.

Key Findings

Of all the aspects analysed, the most relevant aspects of the overall analysis are detailed in the following summary:

HUMAN RESOURCES

The Institution considers diversity as an asset and applies recruitment measures and protocols that guarantee equal employment opportunities. However, according to the survey responses, part of the IRB Barcelona community seems to be unaware of such measures and protocols.

Status of Gender Equality inside the Institution

The gender dimension is integrated in the data collection of the Human Resources Department: all quantitative data of the institute's employees are disaggregated by gender and also by nationality.

Successful applicants by gender, including research and research support staff (scientific platforms and administration area):

2017: Women 20 - Men 10

2018: Women 24 - Men 26

2019: Women 20 - Men 21

In terms of career progression, no protocols with a gender perspective are in place at IRB Barcelona. However, in reference to the sub-area of professional retention, the exit interviews that all employees carry out when leaving IRB Barcelona, reveal that there is no common factor related to gender issues.

With regard to career breaks, the percentage of career interruptions in the last 5 years is significantly higher for women than for men (80/20% respectively), these being related mostly to maternal leave.

Career breaks related to maternal leaves in the last 5 years

80%
Female

20%
Male

EQUALITY AND DIVERSITY COMMITTEE

IRB Barcelona implemented its first Equality Plan in 2011, which was active until 2016. The institute currently has a second Equality Plan, which covers the period 2017-2021.

Also, in 2015 IRB Barcelona created the Equality and Diversity Committee (EDC), which currently comprises 11 members.

In terms of gender budget, IRB Barcelona allocates a specific budget to the EDC to carry out specific activities.

This research has been carried out by IRB Barcelona in the context of CALIPER project through the funded European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 873134.

Status of Gender Equality inside the Institution

GOVERNANCE

The main area for improvement in institutional governance lies in the under-representation of women in some of IRB Barcelona's decision-making bodies. This is directly related to the number of women occupying the position of Group Leader (3 women versus 24 men). The recent implementation of a new protocol for the gender-sensitive recruitment of group leaders is an opportunity in this regard. A new research group led by a woman has already been incorporated in 2021.

INSTITUTIONAL COMMUNICATION

The topic of gender equality is increasingly present in the Communications department and efforts are being made to ensure that IRB Barcelona's internal and external communications reflect diversity and gender equality.

RESEARCH

IRB Barcelona research groups are aware of the gender perspective in the content of their research, as defined by funding agencies and scientific journals.

STUDENT SERVICES

In terms of student services, there are some initiatives, such as "Noies al lab" and "100tífiques", that contribute to the visibility of women at IRB Barcelona and encourage young women to get involved in STEM studies.

There is current gender balanced situation between male and female students at master's and PhD level thus, there are no specific initiatives aimed at guiding students in their professional development from a gender perspective.

Status of Gender Equality inside the Institution

TECHNOLOGY/ INNOVATION TRANSFER TO MARKET

In general, calls for innovation projects are increasingly aware of the need to mainstream gender equality and some of them already ask innovation teams to be gender-balanced. In addition, the gender dimension consideration is increasing in the context of the proposals.

Currently, 3 of the 6 spin-offs created at IRB Barcelona have a female CEO.

INTERSECTIONALITY

With the experience accumulated in recent years, the Equality and Diversity Committee (EDC) is evolving from a binary approach to equality towards a broader and more intersectional approach, taking into account other social aspects that converge and influence gender equality, such as social class, race, the existence of disability, and sexual or gender orientation, among others.

Status of Gender Equality in the Innovation Ecosystem

The External Assessment has two sections. The first section consists of an analysis of the legal and policy framework at national level while the second is focused on national and regional Innovation Ecosystems.

In the first section, an analysis of the national, regional and local legal and regulatory context was carried out, complemented by a Focus Group with internal IRB stakeholders.

In the second section, synergies (existing and/or potential) with external stakeholders have been identified. The information gathered in this mapping was based on: i) a focus group session with IRB Barcelona staff; ii) a survey carried out by the external stakeholders identified in the aforementioned focus group; and iii) an analysis of the centre's networks ("Social Network Analysis"), carried out with software for this purpose.

Key Findings

NATIONAL LEGAL AND POLICY FRAMEWORK

Spain has specific gender equality legislation at both state and regional level.

At State level, the main provisions are the following:

- Spanish Constitution (1978).
- Organic Law 3/2007, of 22 March for the effective equality of women and men.
- Royal Decree Law 6/2019 of 1 March, on urgent measures to guarantee equal treatment and opportunities between women and men in employment and occupation.
- Organic Law 1/2004, of 28 December, on Comprehensive Protection Measures against Gender Violence.
- Law 14/2011, of 1 June, on Science, Technology and Innovation.
- Organic Law 2/2010, of 3 March, on sexual and reproductive health and the voluntary interruption of pregnancy.
- Royal Legislative Decree 2/2015, of 23 October, approving the revised text of the Workers' Statute Law,

Status of Gender Equality in the Innovation Ecosystem

- Law 39/1999, of 5 November, to promote the reconciliation of work and family life for workers.
- Royal Decree 901/2020, of 13 October, which regulates equality plans and their registration and amends Royal Decree 713/2010, of 28 May, on the registration and deposit of collective bargaining agreements.
- Royal Decree 902/2020 of 13 October on equal pay for women and men.

At the regional level, in Catalonia the main provisions are the following:

- *Estatut d'Autonomia de Catalunya (2006).*
- *L 17/2015247 addressing equality between men and women.*
- *L 11/2014248, which guarantees the rights of LGBTI people.*
- *Law 19/2020, of 30 December, on equal treatment and non-discrimination.*
- *Law 5/2008, of 24 April, on the right of women to eradicate gender-based violence.*

It should be noted that special provisions are foreseen with regard to companies. In this regard, RDL 6/2019 establishes the obligation of all companies with a workforce of more than 50 people to implement Equality Plans.

Law 14/2011 on Science, Technology and Innovation establishes specific measures for the implementation of the gender perspective in Higher Education, the requirement of equal composition of all evaluation commissions in the scientific career and all committees, the integration of the gender dimension in the content of research, the collection of data disaggregated by sex, and the mention of carrying out staff selection and evaluation processes without gender bias.

ANALYSIS OF NATIONAL INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS

STEM Students

According to the data collected, there is a slight gender imbalance among students in STEM disciplines in Secondary Education, which increases significantly in Higher Education. It is important to note that this imbalance is not present in all STEM disciplines but in studies related to technology, ICT and engineering. In this regard, the OECD report "Education at a Glance 2017" warns of the gender gap in technical studies in Spain, which have an average percentage of women of 12%.

Status of Gender Equality in the Innovation Ecosystem

Patent authorship and fundraising for start-ups

The data provided show that women are under-represented, both in patent filings (24.4% of patent filings were made by women) and in obtaining start-up funding (18%).

SOCIAL NETWORK ANALYSIS (SNA)

Conducted through a network analysis tool provided by the project, the analysis of IRB Barcelona's networks included 47 institutions. The main findings of the analysis are:

- IRB Barcelona maintains stable collaborations with a large number of stakeholders from different sectors: research funding institutions, research centres, universities, NGOs and companies.
- IRB Barcelona is a member of BIST (Barcelona Institute for Science and Technology), establishing most of its collaborations with the other members of this institution.
- 18 of the 47 collaborations are led by women.
- Most of the collaborations related to business/industry are led by men.
- 9 of the 47 collaborations take into account gender issues.

According to the results of a Focus Group conducted with IRB Barcelona members and which formed part of the External Analysis, all IRB external collaborators have gender equality on their agenda. In this regard, it is worth noting that IRB Barcelona and the Human Resources departments of the organisations that make up BIST, constantly participate in working groups with the aim to analyse gender equality plans, salary audits and conciliation measures.

Status of Gender Equality in the Innovation Ecosystem

External stakeholders conducted a survey, through which they reported that gender inequalities are still evident in the structure of the organisations ("glass ceiling"), as well as the absence of gender mainstreaming in training and teaching content.

This research has been conducted in the context of Horizon 2020 project, CALIPER.

The results will be used for the project's next implementation phases.

IRB Barcelona is one of the 9 Research Organisations across Europe which participates in CALIPER to develop a **Gender Equality Plan (GEP)** and engage the local Innovation Hubs to transfer the gained knowledge beyond academia.

Discover more about CALIPER

This research has been carried out by IRB Barcelona in the context of CALIPER project through the funded European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 873134.